

TEACHING ATTRIBUTES AND STUDENT OUTCOMES: EVALUATING TEACHERS EFFECTIVENESS AT THE PRIMARY LEVEL IN DISTRICT KOTLI, AJ&K

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Abstract

This research was aimed at exploring the level of teachers' effectiveness at the primary schools in District Kotli, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. It also focused on measuring how teachers' effectiveness related to their teaching characteristics and how these influenced the students' academic performances. A descriptive survey design was used for the study. The target group consisted of 756 female teachers working in the government primary schools of District Kotli. Through stratified sampling, 300 teachers were chosen to be studied. A questionnaire on a five-point Likert scale was developed after reviewing the literature and expected outputs. The questionnaire was also validated by subject matter experts and pilot testing was done with 10 teachers who were not included in the sample. The data were collected by the researchers personally. For data analysis, simple percentages and mean scores were used. The results indicate the strengths like strong subject knowledge (95.8%), clear communication (86.6%), creativity (85.1%), and active engagement (82.8%). Nonetheless, there are critical gaps. For example, only 46.7% prepare lesson plans regularly, 40.2% use teaching aids, and 57.9% summarize lessons. Besides, 11.9% of teachers confessed to unequal treatment of students. Although teachers have some main characteristics, the lack of planning, the use of modern techniques, and equity may lead to poorer learning outcomes and rising dropout rates. The research recommends that lesson planning may be made compulsory, audiovisual aids may be provided, and training on equitable teaching practices may be arranged.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is the deliberate, systematic process of facilitating learning and development in students. However, modern educators understand that teachers cannot be mere conveyors of knowledge. They also need to teach people how to think critically, to practice skills, and to get them ready for a full participation in society (Najib, 2017). Teaching and learning form an inseparable couple in the educative process, just like the relationship

between a parent and child. The teacher prepares the stage and the student, learning, takes the lead role in this process of give and take (Iqbal, 2018). Without students' active involvement, the teacher is not able to deliver the best possible learning experience. When the teacher is working as a facilitator, they design the environment that allows learners to build up their understanding and grow their skills (Blankie, Case, & Jawitz, 2010). This part of teaching calls for command

over the subject, knowledge of the art of teaching, human skills, and the ability to set up inviting and encouraging learning situations.

It is not only about the teacher's personality traits: being broad in outlook, having timely sense of humor, being considerate and able to establish bonds in the classroom (McGreevy, 1990; Kanan & Baker, 2002), but also about knowing how to link content learning with appropriate methods of teaching. A well-planned curriculum would do no good if it wasn't combined with excellent teaching. Teachers are effective when they maintain their commitment to enhancing student learning outcomes. Besides showing reliability, they are analytical thinkers with respect to student needs and they also make concerted efforts to increase student success (Akiri, 2013; Ellett & Teddlie, 2003). At primary stage, teachers are even more instrumental in rolling out foundational education (Hattie, 2009). Besides teaching, teachers are the ones who interpret and enact educational policies to give rise to actual student performances (Suleman, Aslam, & Hussain, 2011).

Besides changing their methods, teachers need to stay abreast with student needs and societal expectations. In the last couple of decades, there has been a gradual change of teaching approaches aimed at solving learning problems more effectively (Edgerton, 2001). Teaching that really works can help a student think critically, reason at an abstract level, and apply knowledge while forming attitudes, developing leadership qualities along the way (Handelsman et al., 2004).

One of a teacher's key abilities is to deliver knowledge that aligns with the national curriculum goals, and also to make the teaching understandable and relevant to students (McBer, 2000). To keep the students actively participating, effective teachers use a variety of teaching methods (Stronge & Tucker, 2000). For example, they use both individual study methods and collaborative group work. Besides, effective teachers also work on improving student-teacher resources that are interactive and meaningful (Hall & Walsh, 2002). Teacher evaluation is a way of accomplishing a number of objectives, e.g. giving feedback to teachers and serving as a tool to help students

learn better (Peterson, 2000; Tucker & Stronge, 2005). Highly effective teachers have explicit, written goals that guide instruction and communicate expectations. Fundamentally, the quality of learning is determined by the quality of teaching.

High quality teachers have high expectations of their students and they believe that their students can succeed. These teachers not only share their lesson plans to clarify the goals of the learning but also possess a thorough knowledge of their subject matter. Besides these, an effective teacher should have self-discipline, a positive attitude, and management skills (Great Schools Staff, 2012).

The aim of the study is to measure the level of teacher effectiveness in primary education of District Kotli, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, with the main focus on teachers' characteristics and their impact on student's academic performance.

Statement of the Problem

Questions persist about the problems teachers face in demonstrating effectiveness and the factors compromising instructional quality in primary education. This study investigates teachers' effectiveness at the primary level in District Kotli AJ&K.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find out teachers' effectiveness in terms of teaching attributes used by teachers at the primary level in District Kotli AJ&K
2. To explore teachers' effectiveness in terms of academic achievements of their students at the primary level in District Kotli AJ&K

Research Questions

1. What is teachers' effectiveness in terms of teaching attributes used by teachers at the primary level in District Kotli AJ&K?
2. What is teachers' effectiveness in terms of academic achievements of their students at the primary level in District Kotli AJ&K?

REVIEW OF THE RELATED LITERATURE**Primary Education in Pakistan**

Only 85% of Pakistani children complete primary education. Primary education typically lasts three to five years, including Play Group, Nursery, and Kindergarten. After pre-school, students progress through junior school (grades 1-5) followed by middle school (grades 6-8). Curriculum commonly includes Computer Science, Arts, ICT, General Science, Modern Languages (Urdu and English), Mathematics, and Islamic Studies. Provincial languages may also be taught. As of 2009, Pakistan's net primary school attendance rate was 66 percent, substantially below the global average of 90 percent, primarily due to low public investment (Adam, 2014).

Perspectives on Effective Teachers and Teaching

Research has regularly studied students' perceptions of effective teachers and has discovered the characteristics of effective teaching. Darling-Hammond (2006) said that "one of the most damaging myths in American education is the idea that good teachers are born and not made," highlighting the significance of teacher education. Prior research puts forward the idea that teaching professions necessitate ongoing development, especially for those teachers who are instructing special populations and who, therefore, need to have communication and professional knowledge skills that are specific (Delisle & Galbraith, 2002).

Studies on the effectiveness of teaching repeatedly determine that students with special needs require special teaching. According to NAGC (2008) "As a matter of fact, well-trained teachers are skillful teachers who consistently make a difference." Teacher accountability, professional standards, and qualifications are extremely important (Welsh, 2011). Effectiveness is measured by changes in student behavior, engagement, and achievement."

Chan (2011) pointed out 25 qualities and 14 competencies of good teaching, which he grouped into four classes: individuality, achieving, regulated work, and change orientations. Improving teachers' skills through education has a significant influence on students' social

development, employment opportunities, and earnings in the future, according to the American Economic Association (2014) (Chetty, Friedman, & Rockoff, 2014).

Principles of Effective Teaching

Effective teaching is first of all understanding the child's mind and then choosing methods accordingly. Teacher methods have to be in line both with the child's nature and the content requirements. To teach successfully, one needs to know students' entering behaviors, their prior knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Quality teaching is thorough planning.

The Teacher as Listener

Students listen and respond to teachers who are good listeners. There is research on the development of student listening skills, but to a lesser extent, there are studies on teacher listening skills. Good listening skills deepen the bond between the student and the teacher. They also create situations where students feel that they matter.

Teacher Behavior and Its Impact

Teaching practice promotes critical thinking, skill development, and concept formation (Croninger & Valli, 2009; Pianta, LaParo, & Hamre, 2008). Positive teacher attitudes create optimal learning opportunities through feedback, questioning, and response selection (Curby, Rudasill, Edwards, & Perez-Edgar, 2011; Hamre & Pianta, 2005; Rubie-Davies, 2007), while negative behavior produces adverse effects (Pössel et al., 2013). Teachers can effectively shape student attitudes through their instructional approaches. Positivity in teaching methods can predict academic performance, while poor grades and lack of student interest often correlate with feelings of hopelessness and discouragement (Roeser, Eccles, & Sameroff, 2000).

Early Childhood Development

From birth to age five, almost the entire brain is changed through experience: physically, socially, emotionally, and intellectually ~ all development happens at once. Quality early childhood

experiences, such as positive teacher-child relationships, can build children's resilience and help them develop to their fullest potential. According to the National Scientific Council on the Developing Child (2007), early development lays the groundwork for lifelong learning and success.

Qualities of Effective Teachers: Student Perspectives

Students in the UK aged 15-19 came up with the 5 major qualities of an effective teacher: adept in building positive relationships and creating supportive environments; knowing individual needs of students; showing teachers' work proves student success; combining education with encouragement; and having a profound knowledge of subject and expertise in teaching.

Problems Faced by Effective Teachers

Teachers face many challenges. The absence of parental support is a significant issue because most parents neither interact with teachers nor are they aware of classroom problems. Another huge challenge is funding, which affects the quality of teaching very deeply. Lack of funding results in very large classes and very few technical facilities and instructional aids (Fatima, 2015). These problems are the biggest for public schools, whereas private schools face them less. Teachers most of the time go back to old methods without help from others. Insufficient funding is the reason why primary education fails most of the time because this level needs a lot of resources for effective implementation.

Measuring and Evaluating Teacher Effectiveness

At the core of measuring accomplished teaching is not just about figuring out who the good and bad teachers are, but rather to support all teachers in their learning and growth. "To get to the bottom of things, we will have to figure out what affects student learning the most, only then will we know how to better prepare our young teachers and support the veteran teachers in becoming accomplished educators," writes Norman (2010). Weisberg, Sexton, Mulhern, and Keeling's (2009) comment was: "We are in deep trouble at the core

our schools have failed to either evaluate instructional performance accurately or act decisively on such information"

When schools fail to develop meaningful measures of teacher performance, evaluation systems shape only a limited role in increasing teacher effectiveness. Weisberg et al. (2009) added that, usually, teacher evaluation systems are not influenced by high-quality empirical research and typically generate little differentiation among teachers.

One of the pieces teacher evaluation frameworks have been misused for is determining effectiveness. As Danielson (2007) puts it, "Frameworks for professional practice are the profession's assurance that the members of a profession hold themselves and their colleagues to high standards of practice." Such frameworks serve as a base and a structure but still open up to different instructional styles. The issue is that Delandshere and Petrosky (2004) raise is that a common set of teaching standards for all teachers can be seen as removing intellectual autonomy. Ladson-Billings (2009) supported this point, "Teacher assessment should move away from a notion of good teaching that is connected to one particular way of teaching."

Student performance are frequently used together with teacher evaluation frameworks. Staiger and Rockoff (2010) admitted, "Teacher effectiveness estimates constructed from student achievement data often represent quite noisy measures and can be considered to have a reliability of about 30 to 50 percent."

Rockoff and Speroni (2010) shared, "Classroom observations with exceptions of very few, have been found to possess a considerable significant power to predict student achievement."

Professional Development

The importance of professional development for improving teacher quality has been recognized worldwide (Bayar, 2014). Hill (2009) states, "Most teachers receive fragmented and often low-quality professional development and learning opportunities." DeMonte (2013) adds, "What teachers receive as professional opportunities to learn are thin, sporadic, and of little use." A shift

from passive, sporadic professional development to active, sustained, job-embedded approaches can cause progression in teaching practice (Stewart, 2014).

According to Taylor, Yates, Meyer, and Kinsella (2011), "Professional development has not recognized that teachers are not a homogeneous population but represent diverse perspectives, experience, ability, and responsiveness to new ideas." Professional development models that are collaborative, learning-focused, and related to practice are more meaningful to teachers (Flint, Zisook, & Fisher, 2011). Effective professional development is characterized by high-quality, relevant, job-embedded, and long-term opportunities for teachers to learn.

Effective Teacher-Student Relationships

The theory of student-teacher relationships explains that teachers develop students' contribution to school. Research indicates that when teachers have close and supportive relationships with students, students are more interested in investing time and effort in academic achievement. Conversely, when teachers have tense relations with students, they more frequently

attempt to modify student behavior (Hamre & Pianta, 2001). The positive impact of teacher-student relationships on academic achievement can be seen across age levels, though it may vary depending on classroom characteristics such as the number of students with behavioral problems, teacher perceptions, instructional approaches, and interactions (Koth, Bradshaw, & Leaf, 2008).

METHODOLOGY

The aim of this research was to use a descriptive survey approach to study the effectiveness of primary school teachers in the District Kotli, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The target population was 756 female teachers of government primary schools. Stratified random sampling was used to select 300 teachers from four Tehsils. A questionnaire on a five-point Likert scale was designed after reviewing the relevant literature and determining the study objectives. Content validity was certified by experts, and reliability was secured by piloting the test with 30 teachers who were left out of the sample. The researchers personally collected the data. The results were analyzed by calculating simple percentages and mean scores.

RESULTS

The results are presented in six thematic tables, each representing a distinct dimension of teacher effectiveness. Each table is followed by interpretive analysis.

Table 1: Domain 1 – Subject Knowledge and Content Mastery

Statement	SA %	A %	PA %	D %	SD %	Mean
I have full grasp on the subject which I am teaching	47.12%	38.31%	10.34%	1.91%	2.30%	4.26
I have enough self-confidence	28.35%	35.24%	14.94%	16.85%	4.60%	3.65
Domain Mean						3.96

Analysis of Subject Knowledge and Content Mastery: The "Content Knowledge and Teaching Proficiency" domain scored a high average across the board, with the mean being 3.96. This result

suggests that the teachers are well versed in the content, have a good level of knowledge, and feel confident in their ability to teach it effectively. Most agreement was found with subject mastery as

the highest endorsement, with 85.43% of teachers expressing they fully understand the subjects they teach (M=4.26). Such primary competency is a must for quality teaching and indicates teachers possess enough knowledge of content. The level of confidence in oneself also showed a positive trend

with 78.53% stating they have enough confidence (M=3.65). On the other hand, 21.45% of teachers admitted to a lack of self-confidence which could lead to a decrease in their effectiveness as instructors as well as their readiness to carry out new methods of teaching.

Table 2: Domain 2 – Communication and Interpersonal Skills

Statement	SA %	A %	PA %	D %	SD %	Mean
I communicate the subject matter clearly before the students	38.31%	39.46%	8.81%	11.49%	1.91%	4.00
I use civilized language with the students	29.50%	34.86%	11.87%	16.85%	6.90%	3.63
I am creative	37.93%	26.05%	21.07%	12.64%	2.30%	3.84
I develop student's interest in lesson	34.09%	40.99%	8.42%	14.94%	1.53%	3.91
I ensure that the students understood me when I am teaching	31.80%	28.35%	8.04%	15.70%	16.09%	3.44
Domain Mean						3.76

Analysis of Communication and Interpersonal Skills: The overall average score for this area was moderate at 3.76, indicating that teachers still have room for improving their communication competencies despite generally performing well. Clear communication was the highest indicator as 86.58% of teachers agreed they communicate their subject matter clearly (M=4.00). This ability is a necessary prerequisite of effective student learning. Creativity was identified at 85.10% (M=3.84), representing among the most popular characteristics highlighting teachers' openness to diverse instructional formats. Developing student interest followed closely at 83.50% (M=3.91), with

the majority of teachers being able to generate time in their lessons to keep students interested. On the other hand, there are 2 issues that stand out due to low scores: merely 72.36% of teachers use polite language (M=3.63) while the other 27.64% admit that they sometimes resort to less appropriate language. The more worrying aspect is that only 60.15% verify students' comprehension of instruction (M=3.44). This means that close to 40% of teachers fail to regularly check for understanding, a serious shortcoming resulting, unbeknownst to most teachers, in quite a number of students being left behind.

Table 3: Domain 3 – Student-Centered Approaches and Responsiveness

Statement	SA %	A %	PA %	D %	SD %	Mean
I advise the students to solve their problems according to their needs	33.33%	37.93%	13.79%	8.05%	6.90%	3.82
I admit my faults pointed out by students	34.86%	40.22%	11.11%	13.79%	0.00%	3.96
I give attention to each student individually	30.26%	37.93%	10.34%	14.94%	6.51%	3.70
I try my best to solve pupil's problems in classroom	29.50%	30.26%	21.07%	10.72%	8.42%	3.61
I am active in the school	34.86%	32.95%	14.94%	8.81%	8.42%	3.77
Domain Mean						3.77

Analysis of Student-Centered Approaches and Responsiveness: The domain mean was assessed to be moderate at 3.77, suggesting that teachers in general had a favorable attitude toward student needs. The willingness to admit one's faults was the strongest aspect of the finding with 86.19% of teachers admitting a mistake when students pointed it out (M=3.96). Such readiness to receive criticism is a sign of modesty and a growth mindset contributing to the learning atmosphere. Support

towards problem-solving was conveyed by 71.26% of teachers (M=3.82), and focus on the individual by 78.53% (M=3.70). Nevertheless, there are significant areas of concern: only 80.84% make a great effort to solve pupil problems (M=3.61), which means that almost 20% do not always address student difficulties. A live school engagement was mentioned by 82.75% (M=3.77), which shows that most teachers are actively involved in school life.

Table 4: Domain 4 – Instructional Planning and Preparation

Statement	SA %	A %	PA %	D %	SD %	Mean
I am well prepared when I come for teaching	23.37%	39.08%	10.34%	18.00%	9.20%	3.49
I prepare lesson plan regularly	19.92%	22.60%	4.21%	38.31%	14.94%	2.94
Domain Mean						3.22

Analysis of Instructional Planning and Preparation: This area produced the smallest

domain mean of 3.22, which suggests very serious deficiencies in the basic teaching practices.

Although 73.83% of teachers claimed that they were well prepared when they arrived for teaching (M=3.49), this self-assessment could be an overestimation if one considers the lesson planning data. The most shocking discovery is that only 46.73% of the teachers who prepare lesson plans earnestly (M=2.94), while 53.25% are disagreeing or strongly disagreeing. Teaching without a plan is improvisation, not a professional practice.

Lesson planning is the way through which teachers make their minds about the objectives of learning, choose the activities that are appropriate, anticipate the difficulties of the students, and align their instruction with the goals of the curriculum. The lack of regular lesson planning most probably results in disconnected instruction absence of clear objectives, and degraded learning outcomes.

Table 5: Domain 5 – Instructional Delivery and Teaching Techniques

Statement	SA %	A %	PA %	D %	SD %	Mean
I make proper use of the blackboard	34.86%	37.16%	4.59%	15.70%	7.66%	3.75
I use material aids in the teaching	4.21%	35.63%	5.74%	12.26%	42.15%	2.09
After finishing the lesson, I summarize it	6.51%	31.41%	19.92%	24.52%	17.62%	2.84
Domain Mean						2.89

Analysis of Instructional Delivery and Teaching Techniques: Respondents gave this domain the lowest average score of 2.89, which indicates that instructional delivery practices are in a dire state. The usage of Blackboard was sufficiently done as 76.61% of teachers conveyed proper use (M=3.75). On the other hand, the percentage of teaching aid usage is extremely low: only 40.22% of teachers use material aids (M=2.09), with 42.15% strongly disagreeing. Audio-visual and concrete materials become especially important at the primary level where young children learn

through their different senses. Lack of such aids compels teachers to depend on abstract verbal instructions, which could be developmentally inappropriate for most primary students. Another aspect where instructional delivery practices suffer severely is lesson summarization task: only 57.86% summarize lessons after completion (M=2.84), whereas 42.14% do not. A summarization is an integral pedagogical component that reaffirms learning and assists students in consolidating their understanding; therefore, the absence of it can lead to lowered retention and comprehension.

Table 6: Domain 6 – Equitable Treatment and Classroom Management

Statement	SA %	A %	PA %	D %	SD %	Mean
I behave similarly to all the students	39.46%	40.99%	7.66%	11.87%	0.00%	4.08

Statement	SA %	A %	PA %	D %	SD %	Mean
It is very graceful to check all homework notebooks regularly	25.28%	33.33%	16.85%	19.54%	4.98%	3.54
Domain Mean						3.81

Analysis of Equitable Treatment and Classroom Management: We found the overall average for this category to be 3.81, which is reasonable but the equity concerns were very serious. The best thing we came up with was the equal treatment item since 88.11% of the teachers informed us that they were treating all students the same way (M=4.08). Nevertheless, 11.89 % confessed that they do not treat all students equally. Although it is a minority, the issue raised here is a significant equity concern. Treating students differently

according to gender, socioeconomic status, ability, or any other characteristics is a violation of the inclusive education principle and the effects on students' self-concept, motivation, and achievement can be negative and lasting. Homework checking was one of the items that 75.67% of the teachers reported doing (M=3.54), whereas 24.33% said they did not consistently check homework which is a practice that may work against raising the level of students' accountability and reinforcement of learning.

Table 7: Domain 7 – Impact on Student Academic Achievement

Category	Indicator	Agreement Rate	Mean Score	Impact on Student Achievement
Positive Contributors	Strong subject knowledge	95.77%	4.26	Enhances content acquisition and academic performance
	Clear communication of subject matter	86.58%	4.00	Reduces misunderstandings; ensures effective instruction
	Development of student interest in lessons	83.50%	3.91	Motivates engagement and sustained effort
	Active school engagement	82.75%	3.77	Provides consistent, energetic instruction
	Willingness to solve pupil problems	80.84%	3.61	Removes barriers to learning; creates supportive conditions
	Individual attention to students	78.53%	3.70	Addresses diverse needs; provides targeted support

Category	Indicator	Agreement Rate	Mean Score	Impact on Student Achievement
Barriers to Achievement	Sufficient self-confidence	78.53%	3.65	Contributes to confident, effective instruction
	Regular use of teaching aids	40.22%	2.09	Deprives students of concrete, engaging learning materials; limits concept development
	Regular lesson plan preparation	46.73%	2.94	Results in fragmented instruction; lack of clear objectives
	Lesson summarization after completion	57.86%	2.84	Reduces retention; limits consolidation of learning
	Equal treatment of all students	88.11%	4.08	Note: 11.89% admitted unequal treatment, which may widen performance gaps

Analysis of Impact on Student Academic Achievement: This domain synthesizes findings across all previous domains to assess how teacher attributes affect student learning outcomes. Several positive contributors to student achievement were identified. Strong subject knowledge (95.77%, M=4.26) directly correlates with students' content acquisition. Clear communication (86.58%, M=4.00) remains an essential factor in the effective instruction delivery while development of student interest (83.50%, M=3.91) is a key factor to engage students and motivate them to put sustained efforts. Individual attention (78.53%, M=3.70) is another

respondents. Lack of teaching aids (40.22% usage, M=2.09), which is the nurturing of a habit of getting to the root of a problem a few students may be comfortable with, was ranked as the most significant barrier depriving primary students with hands-on materials, essential for concept development. This could very well explain poor understanding, especially in abstract subjects. Not having regular lesson planning (46.73%, M=2.94) means that a big number of lessons are without clear objectives and logical sequence. Failure to recap lessons (57.86%, M=2.84) hampers students' capability to consolidate their knowledge and remember the main concepts. Furthermore, 11.89% of teachers confess to unequal treatment of students, which might be the case in perpetuating educational inequalities and harm the motivation and self-esteem of students who are marginalized.

Table 8: Summary of Domain Means

Domain	Domain Mean	Interpretation
Subject Knowledge and Content Mastery	3.96	Strong content expertise
Communication and Interpersonal Skills	3.76	Generally positive communication
Student-Centered Approaches and Responsiveness	3.77	Moderate student orientation
Instructional Planning and Preparation	3.22	Critical deficiencies in planning
Instructional Delivery and Teaching Techniques	2.89	Severe deficiencies in resources and methods
Equitable Treatment and Classroom Management	3.81	Generally fair but equity concerns exist
Overall Mean	3.50	Moderate effectiveness with critical gaps

CONCLUSIONS

This study investigated teachers' effectiveness at the primary level in District Kotli, Azad Jammu and Kashmir. The findings reveal a mixed picture of strengths and weaknesses that collectively define the current state of primary education in the region.

Subject Knowledge and Content Mastery: It can be stated that primary school teachers in District Kotli have in-depth subject knowledge and are well versed with the content they teach. This professional capability is their basic requirement to offer quality teaching and it also serves as a springboard for further mastery.

Communication and Interpersonal Skills: Most of the time, teachers talk clearly, show imagination, and succeed in getting students engaged with the lesson. On the other hand, there is a very large gap in checking for understanding, as almost 40% of teachers do not always check if students have understood the lesson. This lack of

follow-up will necessarily cause more students to be left behind without their teachers' knowledge.

Student-Centered Approaches and Responsiveness: Though teachers admit their mistakes freely and generally try to address student problems, opening themselves up to feedback in this way, the fact that 20% of teachers don't regularly work to solve problems points to the gap in helping these students overcome their learning barriers.

Instructional Planning and Preparation: It is concluded that critical weaknesses exist in fundamental teaching practices. Most teachers do not prepare lesson plans regularly, delivering instruction without adequate preparation or alignment with learning objectives. This absence of planning likely results in fragmented instruction, lack of clear objectives, and compromised learning outcomes.

Instructional Delivery and Teaching Techniques: The vast majority of teachers do not

use teaching aids, depriving young learners of concrete, engaging learning experiences essential at the primary level. Many teachers fail to summarize lessons after completion, missing opportunities to reinforce learning and help students consolidate understanding.

Equitable Treatment and Classroom Management: Most teachers behave in an equal manner to all pupils. However, a considerable number (11.89%) of them confess to treating students unequally. Apart from discrimination issues, this could have a detrimental effect on the children's educational experience and might lead to further educational inequalities.

Impact on Student Academic Achievement: A lack of well-prepared lesson plans, teaching materials, and lesson recaps is probably leading to student disinterest and possibly higher dropout rates. A teacher's refusal or inability to be just to all pupils might lower the self-esteem and motivation of the less fortunate ones.

Considering that primary schooling is what lays the educational groundwork for the children, these discrepancies in effectiveness call for immediate redress. Those pupils who get insufficient teaching during primary school are most certainly going to be burdened with learning deficits that will affect their future education and life chances.

Implications for Practice

For Teachers: Teachers may prioritize lesson planning as essential professional practice rather than optional paperwork. Regular planning improves instructional quality and student outcomes by ensuring alignment between objectives, activities, and assessment. Teachers may incorporate teaching aids into daily instruction; where resources are limited, developing low-cost, locally available materials may compensate for funding constraints. Building the habit of lesson summarization may reinforce learning and help students consolidate understanding. Teachers may consistently check for understanding before moving on, ensuring no student is left behind. Additionally, teachers may

reflect on their own attitudes and behaviors to ensure equitable treatment of all students.

For School Administrators: Administrators may regularly review lesson plans and provide constructive feedback to teachers who neglect this practice. It may be a priority to purchase and repair teaching aids, especially for the primary level where concrete materials are necessary, and may help in handling the problem of the shortage of resources. Organizing professional development sessions focused on lesson planning, use of teaching aids, lesson summarization, checking for understanding, and equitable teaching practices may help build teacher capacity. Fostering supportive school cultures where teachers feel encouraged to try new approaches and engage in peer collaboration may promote continuous improvement.

For Teacher Education Programs: Pre-service training programs could make certain that all graduating teachers have excellent lesson planning skills and comprehend the importance of planning. Training in preparing teaching materials at low-cost using locally available resources may equip teachers to operate effectively in resource-poor settings. Directly tackling prejudice and discrimination can be useful to prospective teachers in identifying and going beyond their own biases. Longer classroom exposures accompanied by mentoring support may help in the establishment of face-to-face translation of theoretical knowledge into efficient practice.

For Policymakers: Education budgets may prioritize the provision of teaching aids and materials for primary schools, particularly in rural and underserved areas. Teacher evaluation systems may incorporate meaningful measures of lesson planning, use of varied instructional methods, checking for understanding, and equitable treatment of students. Sustained investment in teacher professional development may be essential for improving instructional quality.

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